

Amperometric Study on Vanadates of Thallium(I) and its Determination as Pyrovanadate

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The stoichiometry of the compounds, precipitated by the interaction of thalious salt and different alkali vanadates (ortho, pyro, and meta), has been investigated by means of amperometric titrations between the reagents. The end points, obtained from titration curves, provide definite evidence for the formation and precipitation of thalious pyro- and meta-vanadates at pH ranges of 8.4 to 8.6 and 6.1 to 6.4 respectively. The precipitation of thalious pyrovanadate has been found to be quantitative. The amperometric results are accurate and reproducible; hence the titration has been developed as an analytical method for the determination of thallium(I) in solutions.

The literature on vanadates of thallium (I) is meagre. The only available reference is of Carnelley¹ who has reported the formation of a series of thalious vanadates (Tl_3VO_4 , $Tl_4V_2O_7$, $TlVO_3$, $Tl_6V_4O_{13}$ and $Tl_{12}V_{10}O_{31}$) by analytical methods. His results could not, however, be confirmed later on. The present investigation has been undertaken with a view to studying the formation and compositions of thalious vanadates, obtained by the interaction of Tl_2SO_4 and alkali vanadates at different pH values, by means of amperometric titrations and the possibility of developing these titrations as an analytical method for determination of thallium(I) in solution.

EXPERIMENTAL

Vanadium pentoxide, sodium hydroxide, thalious sulphate, sodium nitrate, and gelatin of AnalaR (BDH) quality were used. Thallium in Tl_2SO_4 was estimated as its chromate² and vanadium as V_2O_5 ³. Air-free conductivity water was used for preparing the solutions.

A manual polarograph was used for performing amperometric titrations. A dropping mercury electrode, having the following characteristics: $m = 2.416$ mg./sec., $t = 3.58$ sec., and $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.226$ $mg^{2/3}t^{-1/2}$ at $E_{d.c.} = -1.0$ v (vs. S.C.E.), was used in conjunction with S. C. E. All amperometric titrations were carried out at electric tension of -0.7 v (vs. S.C.E.) in presence of suitable concentrations of $NaNO_3$ and 0.01% gelatin. The titre solution of 20.0 ml was taken in the cell each time; it was swept and stirred by bubbling hydrogen. After each addition of the titrant, the galvanometer deflections were read; the corresponding current values were calculated, corrected for the dilution effect, and then plotted against the volume of the titrant added. The proportionality between Tl^+ ion concentration and its wave height was tested; i_d was found to vary linearly with the concentration.

1. *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1873, 26, 323.

2. Moser and Brukel, *Monatsh.*, 1926, 47, 709.

3. Rose, vide J. W. Mellor, "A Treatise on Quantitative Inorganic Analysis".

Ortho-, Pyro-, and Meta-vanadate Titrations.—Standard solutions of sodium ortho-vanadate were prepared by adding a calculated amount of vanadium pentoxide to boiling NaOH solution of required strength. Alkali pyro- and meta-vanadate solutions were prepared by adding requisite quantities of HNO₃ to orthovanadate solution at 100°. Employing different concentrations of alkali vanadates and thalious sulphate, amperometric titrations were carried out with each of the reagents alternately used as titre in presence of NaNO₃ and 0.01% gelatin. The concentration of the supporting electrolyte was always kept about 50 times more than the titre's concentration. The titrations of metavanadate with thalious salt were performed in presence of 40% ethanol. The results of meta-, pyro-, and ortho-vanadate titrations are summarised in Table I. Only three representative figures (Fig. 1-3) have been given for the sake of brevity.

TABLE I

Concentrations.		Equivalence points (ml).		Ratio
		Calc.	Obs.	Tl ₂ O : V ₂ O ₅ .
Tl ₂ SO ₄ .	Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅ .	Metavanadate: Direct titrations (Fig. 1, curve I).		
M/20	M/100	4.00	4.00	1.000:1
M/50	M/300	3.33	3.35	1.005:1
M/90	M/500	3.60	3.65	1.014:1
M/225	M/1000	4.45	4.40	0.9775:1
		Reverse titrations (Fig. 1, curve II).		
M/120	M/20	3.33	3.35	1:1.005
M/250	M/50	4.00	4.00	1: 1000
M/400	M/75	3.75	3.70	1:0.9865
M/1000	M/175	3.50	3.55	1:1.014
Tl ₂ SO ₄ .	2Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅ .	Pyrovanadate: Direct titrations (Fig. 2, curve I)		
M/20	M/200	4.00	4.00	2.000:1
M/30	M/400	3.00	4.00	2.000:1
M/50	M/600	3.33	3.30	1.980:1
M/90	M/1000	3.60	3.65	2.027:1
		Reverse titrations (Fig. 2, curve II).		
M/60	M/20	3.33	3.35	2:1.005
M/250	M/80	3.20	3.20	2:1.000
M/500	M/150	3.00	3.00	2:1.000
M/1000	M/350	3.50	3.55	2:1.014
Tl ₂ SO ₄ .	3Na ₂ O.V ₂ O ₅ :	Orthovanadate: Direct titrations (Fig. 3, curve I).		
M/20	M/300	4.00	2.75	2.0625:1
M/50	M/600	5.00	3.40	2.004:1
		Reverse titrations (Fig. 3, curve II).		
M/250	M/50	1.33	1.85	2.0.925
M/400	M/100	2.60	3.60	2.0.900

DISCUSSION

A series of amperometric titrations between Tl_2SO_4 and metavanadate solutions (Fig. 1) reveals that Tl^+ and VO_3^- ions combine in the ratio 1:1 forming a white, shining precipitate of thallos metavanadate by metathesis according to the reaction:

Thallos metavanadate is appreciably soluble in excess of alkali metavanadate solution and hence 40% aquo-ethanolic medium was employed for the successful and accurate titrations.

FIG. 1. Direct (ID) and reverse (IR) titrations between Tl_2SO_4 and $Na_2O.V_2O_5$ (meta).

Curve ID—ml of $M/20-Tl_2SO_4$ added to 20 ml of $M/100-Na_2O.V_2O_5$.

.. IR—ml of $M/20-Na_2O.V_2O_5$ added to 20 ml of $M/120-Tl_2SO_4$.

FIG. 2. Direct (ID) and reverse (IR) titrations between Tl_2SO_4 & $2Na_2O.V_2O_5$ (pyro).

Curve ID—ml of $M/20-Tl_2SO_4$ added to 20 ml of $M/200-2Na_2O.V_2O_5$.

.. IR—ml of $M/20-2Na_2O.V_2O_5$ added to 20 ml of $M/60-Tl_2SO_4$.

The pyrovanadate titration curves (Fig. 2) yield a sharp break at the stoichiometric end point ($Tl_2O : V_2O_5 = 2:1$), which corresponds to the precipitation of thallos pyrovanadate as a yellow compound at pH 8.4-8.6, having the molecular composition $2Tl_2O.V_2O_5$ or $Tl_4V_2O_7$. The titration results have been found to be very accurate and reproducible, indicating the quantitative precipitation of thallos pyrovanadate (Fig. 2) according to the equation:

Fig. 3 illustrates the direct and reverse amperometric titrations between thallos salt and alkali orthovanadate. It is interesting to note that the well-defined break in titration curves does not occur at the expected stoichiometric point for the formation of thallos orthovanadate, but on calculation it has been found to correspond to the ratio $Tl_2O : V_2O_5 = 2:1$, suggesting the formation of pyrovanadate $Tl_4V_2O_7$ (Table 1). The precipitation of

thallous pyrovanadate, instead of orthovanadate, may be attributed to the hydrolysis of alkali orthovanadate to free NaOH and pyrovanadate⁴.

FIG. 3. Direct (ID) and reverse (IRR) titrations between Tl_2SO_4 & $3 Na_2O.V_2O_5$ (ortho).

Curve ID—ml of $M/20-Tl_2SO_4$ added to 20 ml of $M/300-3 Na_2O.V_2O_5$.

„ IIR—ml of $M/50-3 Na_2O.V_2O_5$ added to 20 ml of $M/250-Tl_2SO_4$.

(vs. S. C. E.). Table II illustrates the results and accuracy of the method.

TABLE II
Vol. of the soln. taken = 20 ml.

Tl (I) present (mg.)	..	136.20	32.70	16.35	8.175
Tl (I) found (mg.)	..	136.96	32.70	16.35	8.292
Error (mg.)	..	0.70	0.0	0.0	0.117

It is evident from Table II that the amperometric titrations of thallous salt with alkali pyrovanadate solution can be suitably used for determination of thallium (I). The accuracy and reproducibility of the method has been found to be excellent and the reaction offers a simple and rapid method for the determination of even small amounts of thallium (I) with an accuracy of about 1%.

The present investigation confirms the formation and precipitation of pyro- $Tl_4V_2O_7$ and meta- $TlVO_3$ vanadates at pH ranges of 8.4 to 8.6 and 6.1 to 6.4 respectively.

The authors express their sincere thanks to the Council of Scientific and Industrial Research, Govt. of India, for the award of a junior research fellowship to one of them (M.L.M.).

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Received November 4, 1963.

4. Saxena and Mittal, *Chimica Hung.*, in press.
5. Unpublished.